

5: Data-Powered Patents

Citation patterns in granted patents in the field of biology

In 2014, open access data resources were cited by **more than 8,000 patents** in the field of biology. British researchers from Cambridge (affiliated with the Wellcome Genome Campus, ELIXIR, the EMBL, and Ganesha Associates) combined information from different biomolecular data repositories and looked for re-use in industry, uncovering this important result. Their work demonstrates both how academic and industrial innovators can leverage data to advance applied science and the extent of secondary data re-use in the field of biology.

The analysis of data citations in patents

The researchers linked open access scientific literature from Europe PubMedCentral to the metadata in biological repositories, such as the Protein Data Bank, the European Nucleotide Archive, and SureChEMBL. Their efforts were supported by **text mining**, a practice that uses algorithms to look for patterns, trends, and other information. Text mining is possible only when data is properly and consistently managed, which means that the information described in this case study primarily exists as a result of good research data management.

The main aim of the researchers' work was to investigate the secondary use of bioinformatics resources to understand the flow and impact of data in the field of biology. No previous studies addressed this and there was room for highly improving of the indicators used to evaluate the impact and reach of academic work.

The use of biological data sources in official documents such as patents shows that they

don't always concern basic research and that they can be a **"fundamental component of the digital knowledge management framework needed in a modern society"**.

Other implications of the study

This investigation of the impact of biological data on patents highlights the importance of repositories, but it also sheds light on the thorny topic of citations and researcher evaluation. One of the ways **researchers' performance** is assessed is by considering the impact of their work. This is most often approached by analysing indicators such as the number of published articles and citations by other researchers, usually excluding **citations to data**. On the other hand, the above-mentioned work on citations from patents clearly shows how citations of academic articles only show a partial picture. This leads to the conclusion that a more comprehensive assessment of researchers' performance should include robust indicators of data citation in both articles and other types of documents, including scientific and technical documents such as patents, guidelines, reports, or grant applications.

In addition, research funders have been increasing their demands in terms of **open data policies**, thus, it is essential to develop metrics that evaluate how open research data is used. These can offer a range of benefits, including improving reward mechanisms for scientists, supporting the management and sustainability of data repositories, and understanding the societal value of data policies.

Title	5: Data-Powered Patents
Subtitle	Citation patterns in granted patents in the field of biology
Abstract	The analysis of data citation patterns in the field of biology showed how over 8,000 patents were based on publicly available data. While this proves the usefulness of repositories as a whole, it also shows how the evaluation of researchers should consider data citations and alternative sources, too, as these are often key to uncover the broader industrial and societal value of academic research.
Keywords	citations; patents; text mining
Research subject area	BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES
Type of RDM impact/benefit	Efficiency in research and data re-use (e.g., reduce duplication of effort); Methodological impact (e.g., new approaches developed); Socio/Economic impact
Summary Impact Type	Impact on economy and business
Facts and figures	8,000 patents thanks to open data
Original dataset from which the impact arose	
Maturity of the initiative/data source	Recent (<5 years)
Year (e.g., first data release, first output, year of impact)	2014
Organisations involved	University of Cambridge
Academic citations	Bousfield D, McEntyre J, Velankar S et al.(2016). [Patterns of database citation in articles and patents indicate long-term scientific and industry value of biological data resources](http://dx.doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.7911.1) . F1000Research.
Links	https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/text-and-data-mining-copyright-exception http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/policy-and-legal/overview-funders-data-policies http://www.hefce.ac.uk/pubs/rereports/year/2015/metrictide/